

SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS INFLUENCING THE ADOPTION OF “GURA” FISH TRAP TECHNOLOGY IN NIGERIA

Sule, A.M¹ ; Sanni, A.O¹ ;Olowosegun, T¹; Agbelege, O. O² and Olabanji, M. U¹

National Institute for Freshwater Fisheries Research, P.M.B. 6006, New Bussa, Niger State, Nigeria.

²Federal College of Freshwater Fisheries Technology, Alau , Maiduguri, P. M.B 1060, Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT:

The basic premise of extension that agricultural technology will diffuse from more progressive farmers to others in the rural communities is refutable. What is conspicuous in adoption and diffusion of most fishing technologies are basically cost and appropriateness for a large segment of the clientele. A total of one hundred respondents were interviewed using questionnaire in both Lakes Chad and Kainji. Descriptive statistics of mean, percentages and ordered ranking were used to analyse the socio-economic characteristics of the fishers, while t-test was used in determining the significant differences in the socio-economic variables of the two set of respondents. Analysis of result showed that the means of ages for the two sets of respondents were 39 and 33 years, number of years spent on education was 2.8 and 2.3 years, income of N44, 220 and N27, 260 and number of traps as 58.3 and 26.9. The t-test result showed significant differences in the fishers' age, household size, income and the number of traps owned by the two sets of respondents ($P < 0.05$). Perception indices for the “gura” trap technology attributes were found to be high 0.89 and 0.91 respectively indicating that the fishers considered all the attributes of the “gura” technology as very important. Recommendations in the form of regular monitoring and enforcement of appropriate mesh sizes, identifying and considering the indigenous knowledge systems in technology formulation as well as conducting environmental impact assessment on the use the fishing trap were proffered for rational and sustainable use of the technology for fisheries development.

KEY WORDS: Socio-economic, Influencing, Adoption, Gura, Technology, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Adoption is defined as the actual use of a technology on a continuous and large-scale basis. The rate of adoption of improved fishery technologies by fisherfolks is very low. The question is, how appropriate are the technologies developed at the research institutes? Why is low or no adoption not given a critical thought? Indeed change in agricultural technology is one of the accelerators of its development.

Improved technologies are usually released with recommendations in addition to their high cost. The high cost and investment required are some of the impediments for adoption of most of the improved technologies. When developing technologies there is need for a development strategy that takes into cognizance, the socio-economic factors as they apply to the situations of the clientele. The socio-economic factors related to the adoption of new technologies which include personal characteristics of the fisherfolks and the characteristics of the context in which they act are therefore imperatives.

This paper discusses the highlights of the “Gura” trap or “Guran Mali” fishing technology. “Gura” trap or Malian trap was introduced to the Nigerian fishermen by the Malian immigrant fishermen around 1980s, (Sarch and Madakaru, 1995). The trap gained wide acceptance (adoption) in many freshwater bodies in the Northern part of Nigeria. The traps are mostly used during the rising and receding floods. At the peak of the flood, it is usually difficult for the fishermen to operate them though; very few fishermen do (Agbelege *et al* 2001). Malian traps catch all types of fish species but mostly Clarias and Tilapia (Agbelege, *et al*. 2003).

Generally, the effectiveness of the technology in trapping the target fish species resulted in impressive adoption and diffusion rate of the “Gura” trap, hence the desire for the study to probe deeper and understand the rationale behind

the fast dissemination of the technology. Nonetheless, the problem of effectively harnessing new technologies to meet the needs of rural development is a highly complex one that requires careful management given the two themes of development. One is to increase fish production to meet the needs of the teeming population and the other is the conscious desire to prevent the degradation of the natural resources caused by bad fishing practices. The objectives of this study are to give in sights into the adoption behaviour of the fisherfolk with emphasis on socio-economic factors; technology attributes and perception of the fishers on the attributes of the technology as they influence its adoption. It was hypothesized that there were no significant differences between the socio-economic characteristics of the fishers in Lakes Chad and Kainji.

METHODOLOGY

The study areas:

Lake Chad lies between latitude $12^{\circ} 14' 20''$ N and longitude $13^{\circ} 15' 30''$ E south of Sahara within the sahel zone of West Central Africa. It is a very large shallow eutrophic natural lake shared by four West African Countries, Chad 50%, Nigeria 25%, Niger 17% and Cameroun 8%. The shoreline of the Nigerian portion of the lake is characterized by numerous islands that extend for about 256km from the north of River Yobe at Malanfatori in the north to the mouth of El-Beid at Wulgo in the south. The surface area of the lake is not constant as it has been fluctuating between 6000km^2 (Bukar and Gubio, 1985) and LCBC, 1989).

On the other hand, Lake Kainji was formed as a result of the impoundment of River Niger by the construction of Kainji Dam. The impoundment led to the creation of the largest man-made lake in Nigeria in 1968. The lake is located between longitudes $4^{\circ} 20'$ North and $4^{\circ} 45'$ East; and latitudes $9^{\circ} 50'$ and $10^{\circ} 55'$ North. The lake is 136km long, 24km wide at its widest point with an area of 1,250 square kilometers. Though the primary purpose of constructing the dam is the generation of hydroelectric power, the creation of the lake offered opportunities for a variety of development projects such as fisheries, irrigated agriculture and improved navigation from the coast up to the Republic of Niger (KLI, 1977).

The study was conducted in two locations, Lakes Chad and Kainji. The research design for the study was survey and employed the cross-sectional method while the research instrument was questionnaire. The administration of the questionnaire was in two phases, which were during the rising and receding floods in the months of October and May, 2007 respectively.

A two stage random sampling technique was used in this study to get the required number of the respondents in Lakes Chad and Kainji. The first stage involved the selection of five fishing villages in each of the lake areas. The second involved random selection of ten respondents from each of the selected villages in the two lake areas. In all,

50 respondents were selected as sample size for each Lake area making a total of 100 respondents (Table 1). Administration of the instrument was in two phases, during the rising and receding floods in October and May, 2007.

Descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentage, mean and ranking were used for analysis. Student's t-test was also used to compare the socio-economic variables of the respondents. To measure the fisher folks' perception of the technology attributes, they were asked to indicate their degree of perception on seven technology attributes on a 2-point scale in accordance with Ajayi (1998) and Anyanwu (2002). The response categories and their weighted scores were as follows: Important = 1; not important = 0. The mean (\bar{X}) perception score for each of the 7 attributes was computed by dividing the total perception score by the total number of respondents (50) for each lake area. The mean (\bar{X}) technology attribute perception score was dichotomized as 0.0 - 0.49 = not important and 0.5 - 1.0 = important. The technology attribute perception index of the fisher folks was calculated by dividing the grand mean (\bar{X}) perception score by the total number of technology attributes (7).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows a total sample size of one hundred respondents from ten fishing communities in the two lake areas. Five communities were selected with ten respondents each making a total of fifty for Lake Chad and same for Lake Kainji.

Table 1: Names of Villages and number of respondents sampled

Lake Chad	Number of respondents	Lake Kainji	Number of respondents
Daban Shata	10	T. A. Danbaba	10
Dumba	10	T. A. Angulu	10
Lagos Maiyashi	10	Shagunu	10
Abuja	10	Wara	10
Madayi	10	Garafini	10

Table 2 presents data on the socio-economic characteristics of the fisher folks in the two lake areas. Entries in the table indicated that while (40%) of the respondents in Lake Chad were between the age range of 34-41 years, much younger fishers (26-33 years) were the majority (54%) in Lake Kainji. However, the mean ages of the respondents in the two Lake areas were 39 and 33 years respectively. Nonetheless, the ages of the respondents in the two lake areas are in the innovative category of adopters and are in their economically active years as confirmed by the conventional studies of Roger (1995); Adeoti and Ibitoye (2002) and Fanikayode and Oloruntoba (2002), where younger people are regarded as more innovative, responsive and adaptive to change than the older people who prefer to stick to traditional practices for risk aversion.

Educationally, the mean numbers of years spent by the respondents in the study areas were 2.8 and 2.3 years respectively. Though, there exists disparity in the mean years spent on education in the two study locations, there was a general low literacy level among the two sets of respondents as a larger chunk of 68-70% were not educated.

The implication of this is that for any technology to be successfully transferred and adopted the technology itself has to be self appealing in its attributes or more effort has to be put on awareness creation and persuasion in order to generate the needed interest for its adoption.

Data on household size indicated large mean household sizes for both sets of respondents. While the mean household size for a respondent in Lake Chad was 9.6 that of Lake Kainji were 7.4. These values are considered large and a welcome advantage for the fishers as more hands would be available for easing the labour involved in the use of the technology for fish production in the lakes. The mean monthly income level of the respondents in lakes Chad and Kainji were ₦44, 220 and ₦ 27, 260 respectively. This means that by virtue of their income from

the use of the fish traps, the Lake Chad fishers are much more financially buoyant than their counter parts in Lake Kainji. This is probably due to the difference in the scale of fishing activities using the traps, differences in the size of the traps and amount of traps owned favoured the Lake Chad fishers.

The mean numbers of traps at the disposal of the fishers from the two lake areas are 58.3 for Lake Chad fishers and 26.9 for Lake Kainji fishers. This observed difference in the number of traps could in turn be explained by amount of money available with each of the fisher folks for the procurement of the technology.

Table 2: Socio- economic characteristics of the respondents in Lakes Chad and kainji.

Socio-economic characteristics	Lake Chad		Lake Kainji		
	Freq.	%	Lake	Kainji	
Age (yrs)					
18-25	3	6	6	12	(\bar{X}) Age
26-33	6	12	27	54	L. Chad = 39 years
34-41	20	40	11	22	L. Kainji = 35 yrs
42-49	18	36	4	8	
50-57	3	6	2	4	
Total	50	100	50	100	
Education					
Tertiary	-	-	-	-	-
Secondary	5	10	3	6	
Primary	4	8	7	14	(\bar{X}) No. of yrs in education
Quranic	7	14	5	10	L. Chad = 2.80
None	34	68	35	70	L. Kainji = 2.30
Total	50	100	50	100	
Household size					
1-5	7	14	10	20	
6-10	24	48	32	64	(\bar{X}) HHS
11-15	14	28	7	14	L. Chad = 9.6
16-20	3	6	0	0	L. Kainji = 7.4
21-25	2	4	1	2	
Total	50	100	50	100	
Income (N000)					
10-30	18	36	37	74	(\bar{X}) = income
31-50	18	36	12	24	L. Chad = N44,220.00
51-70	8	16	1	2	L. Kainji = N27,260.00
71-90	4	8	-	-	
> - 90	2	4	-	-	
Total	50	100	50	100	
No. of traps owned					
10-30	15	30	43	86	(\bar{X}) No of traps owned
31-50	15	30	7	14	L. Chad = 58.3
51-70	9	18	-	-	L. Kainji = 36.9
71-90	5	10	-	-	
> - 90	6	12	-	-	
Total	50	100	50	100	

The result of the t-test analysis of the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents presented in table 3 showed that there exists significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the fishers age, household size, income and the number of traps owned by the respondents in the two Lake Areas. However, the result showed that there was no significant difference in the level of education of the two set of fishers in Lakes Chad and Kainji. It could therefore be seen that fishers' age, household size, income and the number of traps owned are important factors which influenced the respondents' perception of the attributes of the technology in the two lake areas.

Table 3: T-test result of the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents in Lakes Chad and Kainji.

Socio-economic Variables	Lake Chad	Lake Kainji	Decision
Age:			
Mean values	39.34		
t-stat	3.91	33.0	Reject Ho
t-critical (2 tail)	2.00		
Education			
Mean values	2.78		
t-stat	0.51	2.34	Accept Ho
t-critical	2.00		
Household size			
Mean values	9.62		
t-stat	2.50	7.94	Reject Ho
t-critical	2.01		
Income			
Mean values	44.2		
t-stat	5.51	27.3	Reject Ho
t-critical	2.01		
No of traps owned			
Mean values	58.3		
t-stat	5.86	26.9	Reject Ho
t-critical	2.009		

Ho = null hypothesis, Degree of freedom = 49, $P < 0.05$.

The sources of information on “gura” technology was sought from the fishermen in both lakes and classified into personal and impersonal information sources as shown in table 4. The primary goals of the various sources are to create awareness by diffusing among potential adopters on useful and practical information and encourage its application. Personal channels involved a one-to-one interaction between sender and receiver and it enables the sender to tailor the message more appropriately and react to the receiver through a feedback mechanism (Katz, *et al*, 1963). Thus, they tend to be more effective than impersonal channels in transmitting information on technology among the resource poor and illiterate clientele.

The result of the study on Table 4 showed that the personal information source (Fellow Fishermen/neighbours) was the only information source responsible for the “gura’ technology adoption. Hence, 100% of the respondents obtained their information from fellow fishermen/neighbours. The implication is that the technology did not emanate from the research institutes. It was based on indigenous knowledge system and therefore enjoyed no formal extension dissemination strategies.

Table 4: Sources of information

Sources of Information	Percentage	
	Lake Chad	Lake Kainji
Extension workers	-	-
Fellow fishermen/neighbours	100	100
Radio farm programmes	-	-
News letter	-	-
Research bulletins	-	-
Television farm programmes	-	-
Total	100	100

Table 5 showed the mean ratings and rankings of the seven attributes of the “gura” trap fishing technology by the respondents in Lakes Chad and Kainji. Analysis of these attributes showed that in Lake Chad the fishers considered the technology to be cheap and affordable (\bar{X}) = 1.0) with minimum price of N500 and maximum of N1000 per unit as the most important attribute. The trap being readily available and ease of operation were considered as second most important attributes of the technology. (\bar{X}) = 0.96). However, the attribute that the catches attract better price was the least important attribute (\bar{X}) = 0.70) of the technology for the Lake Chad respondents.

On the other hand, fishers in Lake Kainji considered the ease of operation of the technology and its compatibility with the existing practice as the most important attribute (\bar{X}) = 1.0) of the technology. The perception of the attribute of the technology that it is cheap and affordable was the least important attribute to Kainji Lake respondents. The implications of these results are that what the Lake Chad fishers considered as cheap and affordable might not be seen that way by the Kainji Lake Fishers. This might probably be due to the fact that the Lake Chad fishers are wealthier than their Lake Kainji counterparts. Secondly, Kainji Lake fishers tended to prefer a technology that is compatible with the existing practice and easy to operate.

Analysis also showed that the mean ratings of the perception scores for the two sets of respondents in the two Lake areas ranges from a minimum of 0.70 to 1.0 which showed that all the ‘gura’ trap fishing technology attributes are considered important by the fisher folks. Similarly, the perception index of 0.89 and 0.91 for lakes Chad and Kainji equally showed that all the technology attributes are perceived very important by the respondents in the study areas.

The overwhelming importance of the attributes of “gura” trap fishing technology and its acceptance by the fishers in both lake areas stemmed from the fact that many technologies designed for agriculture are basically inappropriate for a large segment of the clientele, and therefore the solution lies in the design of appropriate technology (Morrison *et al*, 1984). Hence, if technology which is appropriate for the resource poor farmer can be designed, adoption and diffusion can proceed from that type of farmer to the aggregate rather than the other way round (Rogers, 1983).

Therefore, small farmers will adopt appropriate technology, if it is economically and technically superior for their farming or fishing systems, just as rapidly as the larger, so called “progressive” farmers (Luning, 1982). Thus, ‘gura’ fishing trap technology tends to satisfy the above conditions of appropriate technology and thence its adoption and diffusion is self propagating. This finding confirmed with consistency what was discovered in a previous study by Sule *et al*. (1994) that for a fishery innovation to be adopted, the equipment has to be cheap or loans have to be made available to facilitate adoption; the catches have to look attractive; the operation has to be simple, and maintenance facilities have to be made available while the technique should be compatible with already existing practices.

Table 5: Fisher folk’s perception of the attributes of the “gura’ trap fishing technology.

S/No	Technology Attributes	Lake Chad		Lake Kainji	
		Mean rating	Rank	Mean rating	Rank
1	Cheap and affordable	1.0	1 st	0.74	7 th
2	Readily available	0.96	2 nd	0.90	5 th
3	Compatibility with existing practice	0.94	4 th	1.0	1 st
4	Catches very well	0.86	5 th	0.94	3 rd
5	Catches attracts better price	0.80	6 th	0.88	6 th
6	Catches are hauled live	0.70	7 th	0.92	4 th
7	Ease of operation	0.96	2 nd	1.0	1 st
	Total mean scores	6.22		6.38	
	Perception index	0.89		0.91	

Explaining adoption behaviour on innovativeness as an individual trait indicates unwillingness, and conceals the inability to adopt. In essence, a fisher or fish farmer may be willing to adopt an innovation but his socio-economic status might be the major factor for his/her inability and not necessarily unwillingness.

For the very low cost and other appealing attributes of the ‘gura’ fish trap technology, its diffusion was like an inferno even without any formal disseminating efforts from any extension agents. Hence, the resource poor fisher folks are not only unable to capitalize on the benefits of improved technologies but are placed at a further competitive disadvantage by those who can.

CONCLUSION

The diffusion of the ‘gura’ technology is simply the result of individual adoption decisions facilitated by interpersonal information sources. The overwhelming factors responsible for the adoption are the technology attributes which tallied with the expectation of the fishermen. The observed variation among the fishers from the two study sites over which attribute most appeal to the respondents was engendered by the differences in their socio-economic characteristics.

However, the problem of effectively harnessing new technologies to meet the needs of rural development is a highly complex one involving all the stakeholders with the government as a regulating entity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are therefore proffered for proper management of Gura fish trap technology for sustainability.

1. There is an urgent need to check the use of under mesh sizes and water channel fencing by the research Institutes, Federal Department of Fisheries and States Fishery Departments in their areas of jurisdiction.
2. The finding of this study tends to underscore the importance of indigenous knowledge system. Hence for technology generation and adoption to be more successful, there is the need for the participation of the clientele who are the intended beneficiaries to be carried along from inception and in line with their indigenous knowledge system.
3. It is necessary to conduct further studies on the environmental impact assessment arising from the wide acceptance and use of the “gura” trap fishing technology. This will provide avenue for a more rational decision on ways of regulating the impacts of similar technologies on fish species abundance and depletion in lakes, deforestation and ecosystem balance.

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Corresponding Author:

Sule, A.M

National Institute for Freshwater Fisheries Research, P.M.B. 6006, New Bussa, Niger State, Nigeria.